

Stanovisko / Opinion

Hodnotenie rizika uplatnenia *Eucryptorrhynchus brandti* (Harold) resp. *E. chinensis* (Olivier) ako prostriedku biologického boja proti pajaseňu žliazkatému (*Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle)

Risk resulting from introduction of two native (Chinese) pests of invasive tree-of-heaven, *Eucryptorrhynchus brandti* (Harold) and *E. chinensis* (Olivier), into Slovakia

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1. MANDÁT NA HODNOTENIE RIZIKA

„Hodnotenie rizika uplatnenia *Eucryptorrhynchus brandti* (Harold) resp. *E. chinensis* (Olivier) ako prostriedku biologického boja proti pajaseňu žliazkatému (*Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle)“

Experti národnej odbornej vedeckej skupiny (NOVS) pre biologické riziká predložili na 15. rokovaní Komisie pre bezpečnosť potravín a výživu návrh na hodnotenie rizika uplatnenia *Eucryptorrhynchus brandti* resp. *Eucryptorrhynchus chinensis* ako prostriedku biologického boja proti pajaseňu žliazkatému (*Ailanthus altissima*).

Komisia pre bezpečnosť potravín a výživu jednohlasne odporúčala návrh na hodnotenie rizika prijať a ako riešiteľ a navrhla Ing. Petra Ferusa, PhD.

Odbor bezpečnosti potravín a výživy (OBPV) prijal mandát a zostavil Dohodu o vykonaní práce na vypracovanie hodnotenia rizika do 71 hodín v termíne od 1. 4. 2013 do 30. 11. 2013. Osnova hodnotenia rizika je jednotná pre všetky stanoviská zadávané OBPV a je súčasťou tohto mandátu. Hodnotenie rizika bude pred jeho prebratím OBPV podrobené verejnej diskusii v rámci NOVS pre biologické riziká. Preberacie konanie bude ukončené až po zodpovedaní všetkých pripomienok.

Vypracovaním a zverejnením hodnotenia rizika na webovej stránke Ministerstva pôdohospodárstva a rozvoja vidieka Slovenskej republiky (MPRV SR) a na Platforme pre výmenu informácií Európskeho úradu pre bezpečnosť potravín (IEP EFSA) sa splní čl. 2 bod a) odsek 3 Dohody medzi EFSA a MPRV SR o zabezpečení výmeny informácií o nepretržitom hodnotení rizika a pripravovaných názoroch v SR.

2. Abstrakt

Pajaseň žliazkatý (*Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle), pôvodom z Číny/Taiwanu, v minulosti vysádzaný ako okrasný strom, predstavuje v súčasnosti vážny ekologický a ekonomický problém pre Slovensko ako aj mnohé ďalšie európske krajiny. Široko používané mechanické a chemické prostriedky jeho regulácie sú však dosť nákladné a často majú len nepatrný efekt. Z tohto dôvodu je tu požiadavka na špecifický, ekologický a vysoko efektívny prostriedok s malými/žiadnymi vedľajšími účinkami. Do úvahy pripadajú dva druhy hmyzu, *Eucryptorrhynchus brandti* (Harold) a *E. chinensis* (Olivier), v domovine prirodzený škodcovia menovanej dreviny.

Z dostupnej literatúry vyplýva, že stredoeurópska klíma vyhovuje uvedeným chrobákom z hľadiska ich prežitia a založenia populácie. Napriek tomu, neexistuje zmienka o ich prítomnosti v Európe, hoci ich introdukcia v minulosti (necielená, s osivom pajaseňa žliazkatého) sa nevyklučuje. Dovoz týchto chrobákov na experimentálne účely (do karantény, Arborétum Mlyňany SAV), podľa nášho názoru, nepredstavuje žiadne riziko pre okolitú vegetáciu, a to pre vysokú druhovú špecifickosť tohto hmyzu v kontexte výberu hostiteľskej rastliny ako pre aj jeho sesilnosť.

Samozrejme, aby sa zabránilo akýmkoľvek ekonomickým škodám, pred tým, ako dôjde ku ich kontrolovanému vypusteniu do prírody, bude nutné zodpovedať otázky týkajúce sa afinity chrobákov k slovenským/európskym hospodársky významným druhom drevín, životného cyklu chrobákov a ich schopnosti prezimovať ako aj otázky týkajúce sa mechanizmu ich účinku na hostiteľské rastliny. Toto sú hlavné ciele nášho bilaterálneho projektu s Taiwanom.

Kľúčové slová: bioregulácia, pajaseň žliazkatý, prirodzený škodcovia, introdukcia, testy v karanténe

Abstract

Tree-of-heaven (*Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle), in the past introduced from China/Taiwan as an ornamental species, represents presently a large ecological and economical problem. Widely used mechanical and chemical regulation of this invasive tree is relatively expensive and usually of low effect. Therefore, there is a need of a nature-friendly, efficient target medium with small/no side effect. Two weevil species, native pests of this tree, *Eucryptorrhynchus brandti* (Harold) and *E. chinensis* (Olivier), mostly meet with these expectations.

From available literature we know that Middle-European climate can be suitable for their survival and population establishment. Despite of this, there is no evidence on their presence anywhere in Europe, although their unintentional past introduction (with sowing material of tree-of-heaven) is not excluded. However, we assume that insect introduction for experimental purposes (into quarantine conditions, Mlyňany Arboretum SAS) would not represent any danger for surrounding vegetation because of their high host species specificity and sessileness.

Of course, to avoid any future economic loss, questions concerning their affinity to Slovak/European economically important woody plants, their life cycle and overwintering ability as well as mode of their action must be answered before controlled release into nature. These are the main objectives of our applied project with Taiwan.

Keywords: bioregulation, tree-of-heaven, native Chinese pests, introduction, quarantine testing

3. Introduction

Ailanthus altissima (Mill.) Swingle is a thermophilic deciduous tree reaching 20-25 m altitude, which originates in Southern, Central and Eastern China, Taiwan, Southern part of Korean peninsula and Japan. It represents a woody plant species with interesting characteristics for human: fast growth of quality wood, decorative appearance of even pinnate leaves, inflorescence, fruits and bark, content of medically effective compounds, as well as recently discovered bio-pesticides, pre-determining it for use in forestry, horticulture, alternative medicine, and agriculture (Lawrence et al., 1991; Heisey, 1996; Skalická, 1997).

Figure 1: Worldwide areas affected by invasive tree-of-heaven (*Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle). Source: Kowarik and Säumel (2007).

The first mention of its occurrence in Europe comes from 1751 (in France). Important role in its distribution in Central European space at the beginning of 19th century played Lednice plant nursery. Finally, in fifties of the past century, more individuals were planted in Slovakia (in Bratislava), as well (Jurko and Šomšák, 1958; Benčať, 1982). Mlyňany Arboretum, Slovak Academy of Sciences enlarged its plant collection by this species in 1966, when research collective organized an expedition to China.

However, today positive attributes of this plant species is obscured by its uncontrolled spreading (Figure 1) from urban into rural environment (Landenberger et al., 2007) and impairing natural and semi-natural ecosystems (from recent works e.g. Kota et al., 2007;

Gomez-Aparacio and Canham, 2008;) with their services, thus directly and indirectly influencing human wellbeing (Binimelis et al., 2007). In past decades it became one of the 100 European as well as world worst alien organisms (GISD, DAISIE). No wonder, when taking into account its reproductive potential (in one tree hundred thousands of samaras can form) combined with vegetative sprouting from root system (Kowarik, 1995), and allelopathic suppression of surrounding vegetation (Dayan et al., 1999).

Only a few attempts of costs calculation regarding alien plants regulation and landscape restoration, can be found in literature (Williamson, 1996; Pimentel, 2009). But our survey revealed only one collective describing expenses of *Ailanthus* management. Luz-Lenzano Caceres and Gerold (2009) estimated 5 million EUR yearly costs for its uncontrolled spread in Hesse, Germany. Moreover, 1.5 million EUR they issue for healing allergies caused by *Ailanthus* pollen (Ballero et al., 2003).

In the worldwide tree-of-heaven regulation usually mechanical and chemical methods have been utilized. For instance, in a study of Constan-Naya et al. (2010) effect of cut stump, double cut stump and cut stump with glyphosate application on *Ailanthus* regeneration were tested. They found that only the cut stump with glyphosate application treatment was able to reduce the long-term growth and spread of this tree. Meloche and Murphy (2006) analysed hand-pulling, mulching and EZject Capsule Injection System filled with glyphosate, as well. The result was similar: cut stump combined with glyphosate was the most effective, least invasive and cost acceptable approach. However, in national parks and other protected areas, application of herbicides is relatively limited.

Therefore, there is a need for specific natural agents, which should effectively eliminate treated trees, only, and cost not much money. Ding et al. (2006) provide an overview of *Ailanthus altissima* pathogens described in native environment of China as well as those observed in continents where this tree has been introduced. As the most promising they find 2 native weevils (*Eucryptorrhynchus brandti* and *E. chinensis*).

4. Pests characterisation

4.1 Insect biology and affinity to the host species

As indicate Ding et al. (2006), *Eucryptorrhynchus brandti* and *E. chinensis* represent the most important pests of tree-of-heaven in China. Up to 100% of medium-large-sized tree individuals were damaged by *E. brandti* and up to 37% died in provinces of central China, as described in original works of Quin (1996) and Ge (2000).

Adults feed on buds, young leaves and petioles of medium- to large-sized individuals. Female beetles lay eggs under the bark. After hatching, larvae bore into trunk and feed on cambium and xylem tissues. Tree mortality is caused by larvae much more than by adults. They are monophagous and do not disperse on long distances. Larvae overwinter under the bark and adults in the soil near host tree. In China, this species has only one generation (Xubing et al., 1999; Teng, 2000; Ding et al., 2006).

Observations in natural conditions rank this species as monophagous. However, choice feeding tests, realised by an American group, showed that *E. brandti* alternatively consumed leaves of corkwood (*Leitneria floridana*) and paradise tree (*Simarouba glauca*), trees native in America (Kok et al., 2008; Herrick et al., 2012). But for oviposition it strictly prefers tree-of-heaven (Herrick et al., 2012). There is no information on possibility to attack European economically important tree species.

4.2 Weevils' requests on climate

As defined by Du et al. (2007), optimal temperature for *E. brandti* growth and development ranges from 20 to 32 °C. Heat and frost limit level at 36 and -17 °C, respectively. Developmental threshold and effective accumulated temperature for the whole generation was 6.72 °C and 1352.8 day.°C. Eggs hatch when moisture between 41 – 92 %. On the other hand, adults overwinter in dry soil, only.

Natural distribution of this weevil almost precisely copies natural distribution of tree-of-heaven (*Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swingle). It comprises following China provinces (Ding et al., 2006; Du et al., 2007): Anhui, Beijing, Gansu, Hebei, Heilongjiang, Henan, Jiangsu, Liaoning, Sichuan, Shandong, Shanghai, Shanaaxi and Shanxi (see map of natural occurrence of tree-of-heaven in Figure 2).

conditions of Europe, despite of partial compatibility (climate types C or D) with Chinese climate (Figure 4).

Figure 4: European climate structure (Köppen-Geiger classification).

4.3 Why are not these weevils present in Slovakia/Europe?

There is no more demand for tree-of-heaven in the presence, thus we can expect exchange of sowing material mainly for experimental use. Although, in second half of the twentieth century, when this species was intensively studied in relation to its use for ornamental and economical purposes in Slovakia (Benčať, 1982) and Europe (Kowarik and Säumel, 2007), some spot introductions of the weevils could occur.

When introduced, they must accompany fruits as the propagation material. Samaras have relatively good germinability - more than 80 % when collected in December (Singh et al., 1992), thus there is no reason for seedlings introduction. However, how could they survive the shipping? We suppose that only *Eucryptorrhynchus* adults could be introduced and it was possible only in the presence of fresh leaves in consignments.

Then, samaras need to be stratified before sowing, so there is only a small space for insects to escape - during manipulation with the sowing material. To stay alive, they need to find a growing host tree soon. If succeed, they can lay eggs and establish a new generation. However, an adverse winter can stop the course of them.

There are too many circumstances to be paid for successful introduction and population establishment. We suppose that these are the reasons responsible for no observation of these insects in Slovakia/Europe, till now.

Nevertheless, when we introduce enough insects and establish their culture(s), they would very probably not represent a danger for surrounding vegetation because of quarantine conditions of breeding as well as large species specificity and sessileness of these weevils.

5. Missing data

5.1 Questions needing to be answered before *Eucryptorrhynchus* release

Although there are some assumptions concerning the *Eucryptorrhynchus* introduction, to avoid potential economic losses, we need to answer following questions before doing that:

1. Would these insets not attack Slovak/European economically important forest and fruit tree species?
2. How sessile they are? How could they spread in space?
3. Can they overwinter in Middle-European conditions? When they do, in what stage(s)?
4. What is the mechanism of tree-of-heaven elimination provided by *E. brandti* and/or *E. chinensis* from physiological point of view?
5. How many generations/seasons are necessary to kill a middle-aged tree-of-heaven individual?

5.2 Description of equipment and procedures for answering these questions

After receiving of permission to import *E. brandti* and/or *E. chinensis* into Slovakia, we intend to establish a culture. For this purpose we reserved an isolated building in Mlyňany Arboretum SAS, after minor reconstruction suitable for breeding and testing of these weevils.

Under three level safety system (main entrance/room door/cage), insects will be produced. In appropriate temperature (22 °C) and moisture conditions, fed on leaves they will lay eggs under the bark of tree-of-heaven billets sealed with paraffin from both sides. A part of adults

will be utilized for no-choice and choice feeding and oviposition tests (Kok et al., 2007; Herrick et al., 2012; Figure 5 and 6). In these tests, affinity to Slovak/European economically important forest (*Fagus sylvatica*, *Quercus petraea*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Betula pendula*, *Populus nigra*, *Picea abies*, *Pinus sylvestris*, *Larix decidua*) and fruit trees (*Malus domestica*, *Pyrus domestica*, *Prunus domestica*, *Prunus persica*, *Cerasus vulgaris*, *Vitis vinifera*) will be ascertained.

Weevil phenology will be studied in isolated external conditions as well as at controlled temperatures in thermostat (at 20, 25, 30 and 35 °C). Simultaneously, their ability to survive winter in conditions of southern Slovakia and their sessileness will be defined (by analysis of insect position from the tree/soil surface).

We also intend to clarify mechanism of tree elimination caused by *E. brandti* and/or *E. chinensis*. From available literature sources we know that larvae of this insect attack cambium layer and xylem tissue, supporting above part of the tree by water and mineral nutrients. Therefore we concentrate on study of water regime in infested trees.

Figure 5: Choice and no-choice feeding tests in seedlings as a part of experimental work of the American research group.

Middle-aged individuals of tree-of-heaven will be infested by larvae in quarantine conditions and following physiological parameters will be recorded in different parts of tree crown during the insect attack (in the season):

1. Relative water content (RWC) – gravimetrically (Slavík et al., 1965)
2. Leaf water potential (Ψ_w) – Scholander pressure chamber (ICT, Australia)
3. Leaf osmotic potential (Ψ_s) and osmotic adjustment (OA) - refractometrically
4. Stomatal conductance (g_s) – porometer SC-1 (Decagon Devices Inc., USA)
5. Xylem sap flow rate (Q_w) – heat field deformation system (EMS, Czech Republic)
6. Biomass production and samara production (Jarvis and Jarvis, 1964).

Figure 6: Oviposition tests in seedlings and trunk/branch billets in Virginia, USA.

5.3 Safety system

Feeding and oviposition tests will be carried out in an isolated building adapted to insect breeding. Insect cultures will be held in quarantine under three level safety system: main

entrance/room door/cage (Figure 7). Under these conditions also controlled phenological studies will be done.

Figure 7: Spaces selected for insect culture and experimental work in Mlyňany Arboretum SAS.

Potential differences in insect development in natural conditions of Mlyňany Arboretum SAS from that in natural forest on mountain ridge of Taiwan as well as overwintering ability of respective weevil stages will be revealed by observation in middle aged tree-of-heaven individuals, which we are already preparing or which are located close to the experimental building. In both cases, tree trunk will be enclosed in a large cage positioned behind a fence, to avoid enter of foreign persons. Moreover, part of tree trunk selected for infestation will be tightly isolated by nylon net sleeve. Thus, we count with building of the three level safety system, again. This isolation system we intend to use also for experiments on detailed explanation of the mechanism of tree dying caused by insects.

Of course, before introduction of any weevil stage, all cultivation/experimental spaces will be prepared and let inspect by responsible organs of Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic.

Tightness of the isolation systems will be controlled daily.

6. Sumár

1. Napriek relatívnej zhode v klimatických podmienkach domoviny analyzovaných chrobákov a Európy ako aj možnej neúmyselnej introdukcii v minulosti, k dispozícii nie sú žiadne dáta o prítomnosti a teda ani životaschopnosti chrobákov *Eucryptorrhynchus* na Slovensku/v Európe. Náš projekt môže zodpovedať otázky životného cyklu tohto hmyzu v stredoeurópskych podmienkach.
2. Domnievame sa, že v prípade dostatočného zastúpenia jedincov oboch pohlaví a prítomnosti hostiteľských stromov, by sa tieto chrobáky mohli v prírodných podmienkach Slovenska/časti Európy rozmnožovať. Je však pravdepodobné, že tieto podmienky dosiaľ neboli splnené.
3. Keďže oba druhy hmyzu sa špecializujú na konkrétny druh hostiteľa a sú sesilné, založenie ich kultúry v Arboréte Mlyňany SAV (v karanténe) by pravdepodobne nepredstavovalo nebezpečenstvo pre okolitú vegetáciu.
4. Spektrum potenciálnych hostiteľských rastlín týchto druhov hmyzu na Slovensku/v Európe nie je dosiaľ známe. Jedným z cieľov nášho projektu je však testovanie ich afinity k hospodársky významným druhom lesných a ovocných drevín.
5. Najvýznamnejšie škody na stromoch pajaseňa spôsobujú larvy živiace sa na ich kambiu a xyléme. Avšak požery listov dospelými jedincami tiež oslabujú tieto stromy. Naším cieľom je tiež objasnenie mechanizmu, ktorým hmyz stromy eliminuje.
6. Záverom sa je možné domnievať, že introdukcia chrobákov na Slovensko/do Európy nebude nebezpečná pre iné druhy drevín, pretože ich kultúra bude izolovaná od okolia ako aj pre ich sesilnosť a špecifickosť pri výbere hostiteľa. Veríme, že naše testy potvrdia výsledky americkej skupiny vedcov a napomôžu kontrolovanému vypusteniu chrobákov do prírodného prostredia.

Summary

1. Despite of climatic fitness and possible unintentional introduction in the past, there is no available data on presence and thus also on viability of any from *Eucryptorrhynchus* species in Slovakia/Europe. Our project can answer questions concerning life cycle of these weevils in Middle-European conditions.

2. We suppose that in case of enough individuals of both sex as well as presence of host trees, these weevils could reproduce in natural conditions of Slovakia/part of Europe. However, it is possible that such conditions still haven't been met.
3. Since both *Eucryptorrhynchus* species are species specific and sessile, their introduction and culture establishment in Mlyňany Arboretum SAS (in quarantine conditions) would not represent any danger for surrounding vegetation.
4. Range of potential host plant species of these insects in Slovakia/Europe is not known. To test their affinity to economically important forest and fruit trees, is one of the project objectives.
5. Detrimental effect of these weevils on host tree-of-heaven individuals is provided by their larvae, feeding on cambium and xylem tissues. However, leaf damage caused by adults also weakens them. We also intend to provide a detailed explanation of the mechanism of host tree elimination.
6. Finally, we suppose that introduction of these insects into Slovakia/Europe would not be dangerous for other vegetation because of culture isolated from the nature as well as high host species specificity and sessileness of the insects. We believe that our tests confirm results of the American research group and help their controlled release into nature.

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8. Abbreviations

DAISIE – Delivering Alien Invasive Species Inventories for Europe / Organizácie pre inventarizáciu invázných druhov v Európe

IEP EFSA – Information Exchange Platform of the European Food Safety Authority / Platforma výmeny informácií Európskeho úradu pre bezpečnosť potravín

GISD – Global Invasive Species Database / Globálna databáza invázných organizmov

g_s – stomatal conductance / vodivosť prieduchov

MPRV SR – Ministerstvo pôdohospodárstva a rozvoja vidieka Slovenskej republiky /
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic

NOVS – Národná odborná vedecká skupina / National group of specialists

OBPV – Odbor bezpečnosti potravín a výživy / Branch of food safety and nutrition

Q_w – Xylem sap flow rate / Rýchlosť toku xylémovej šťavy

RWC – Relative water content / Relatívny obsah vody

Ψ_w – Water potential / Vodný potenciál

Ψ_s – Osmotic potential / Osmotický potenciál